

Additional file 3. Definition of ‘syndrome’

A prerandomisation syndrome or illness *a priori* defined as affecting or possibly affecting neurocognitive development, and which is subdivided in the following categories:

- Genetically confirmed syndrome or pathogenic chromosomal abnormality
- Clearly defined syndrome, association or malformation without (identified) genetic aberration
- Polymalformative syndrome of unknown aetiology
- Clear auditory or visual impairment without specified syndrome
- Congenital hypothyroidism due to thyroid agenesis
- Brain tumour or tumour with intracranial metastatic disease
- Paedopsychiatric disorder (e.g. autism spectrum disorder, (treatment for) attention deficit hyperactivity disorder)

- Severe medical disorder, not primarily neurologic, but suspected to alter psychomotor and/or mental performance
- Severe neonatal problem (e.g. severe asphyxia)
- Severe craniocerebral trauma or near-drowning
- Severe infectious encephalitis or drug-induced encephalopathy
- Infectious meningitis, encephalitis or Guillain-Barré
- Resuscitation and/or need for extracorporeal membrane oxygenation prior to randomisation
- Severe convulsions or stroke prior to randomisation.